

HFNMTC – BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION – DECEMBER 2019
RGN 20- OBS 311– OBSTETRIC NURSING
TIME ALLOWED: 1 ½ HOURS
ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS:

- *Answer all questions*
- *Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet*
- *Each question carries 20 marks.*
- *Read the questions carefully and provide only the relevant answers*
- *Note that any number of points provide beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will attract any mark*

Question One

- a. The innominate bone is composed of three fused bones. Describe the ilium - 8 marks
- b. The breast is an accessory organ of reproduction. Describe the physiology of lactation under the “Let down” reflex - 5 marks
- c. Mention **FIVE (5)** functions of the placenta - 5 marks
- d. The vertex is the highest point on the foetal skull. What structures surround it - 2 marks

Question Two

Madam Busanga 35years old G4P3 was rushed to the labour ward in a Health Center with the history of irregular foetal heart rate. On your assessment vaginally you noticed ruptured membranes, excessive molding, cord prolapse and cervical dilatation of 3cm.

- a. List four criteria for normal labour. - 4marks
- b. Describe the immediate care you will render to her baby? - 10marks
- c. What will be your management for Madam Busanga at the health center? - 6marks

Question Three

- a. Baby Serwaa was delivered one hour ago and you were asked to examine the newborn. What are the features on the head that will help classify her as a normal baby? - 10 marks
- b. What TEN (10) reflexes would baby Serwaa exhibit - 5 marks
- c. Mention FIVE(5) signs and symptoms of subinvolution - 5 marks

